

GOOD PRACTICES & RESEARCH INNOVATION COLLECTED - SQ

ADVISOR NETWORK FOR OPTIMAL FERTILISERS USE

Practice SQ n° 1

CUT&CARRY FERTILIZER

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#Avoid nitrogen losses, grassclover

#SQ, feed, food, oil, Research Innovation (RI), The Netherlands

Short description

→ Instead of 'brown' manure. The pathway over animals gives products but is accompanied by substantial losses of nitrogen. Using the grassclover directly, these losses are avoided. Technically seen there is no problem: no new machinery is needed or other challenges to be overcome.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Put grassclover in the cow (goat) and get back the manure.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? In organic farming the use of manure from conventional animal husbandry is (limited) allowed. This is a situation which is considered as unwanted. If this source of (nitrogen) input is rejected, own nitrogen fixation and reduction of N-losses become essential. Loosing nitrogen by putting grassclover in a cow is

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: We needed ten years of on-farm research to 1. document the way this fertilizer functions, and 2. to find out the practical consequences. The overall outcome is simple: the nitrogen deliverance can be well predicted, and the practice is applicable for a lot of farmers.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes. In some cases, the C&C fertilizer can be cut and brought to another field at the same day, which requires a good organisation of the work. Often the C&C fertilizer is transported to the farm yard and stored there anaerobically, as if it were cow fodder.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** This practice can be applied in all situations where grassclover is part of the rotation.
- **Targeted crop categories:** feed, food, oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** transportation, storage
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** For the moment the practice is economically not attractive. The price of organic manure is competitive. As soon as the use of manure out of conventional husbandry is forbidden, the price of organic manure will rise dramatically and the C&C fertilizer practice will be economically attractive.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** The C&C fertilizer is partly a crop fertilizer and partly a fertilizer. The risk of increased leaching of nitrogen is relevant, but depends on the complete cultivation system, especially crop choice, crop sequence and green manure.
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** agricultural residues

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Yes: the lack of interest to reduce the allowed amount of manure originating from conventional farming
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Probably not, because it is new, and the beneficial aspects are not yet known at the political level.
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: nitrous oxide
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase

- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, as long as you accept a shift from animal production to arable production.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, as long as you strive to reduction of environmental impact and reduction of animal production.
- **Other relevant information:** The use of grassclover as green manure instead of cow feed is for a lot of people a problematic concept.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information Geert-Jan van der Burgt, givanderburgt@gmail.com ; research farm www.spna.nl
; several reports to be found at www.louisbolk.nl

Additional info/links:

<https://www.louisbolk.nl/sites/default/files/publication/pdf/evaluation-planty-organic-2012-2020.pdf>

<https://www.spna.nl/ons-onderzoek/planty-organic-stikstof-telen/>

Practice SQ n° 2

SOIL PASSPORT OR FARM SOIL AND WATERPLAN

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Soil passport, water management

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, Good Practice (GP), The Netherlands

Short description

➔ Based on all the properties of the soil, you'll be able to advise on measurements to decrease the loss of nitrogen and phosphorus to the environment and how to manage water in the best way possible.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Soil information (like type of soil) is available in "bodemdata.nl". In addition, farmers take soil samples, but these are not stored nor accessible in a general database. Water quality is managed by water boards according to the Water Framework Directive.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? To minimise the loss of N and P.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: 1 hour to fill in all the questions and half hour to choose the measurements.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** There are about 85 measurements to choose.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty, all types of soil
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** none

- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, fuel, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** More and better yield.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Great decrease
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** animal manure

Administrative context

- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information BOOT list

Additional info/links:

<https://bedrijfsbodemwaterplan.nl/>

Information is available online: <https://bedrijfsbodemwaterplan.nl/tutorial.html>

Practice SQ n° 3

STRIP-TILL IN SUNFLOWER CROP

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Strip till, sunflower

#SQ, oil, Good Practice (GP), Spain

Short description

- ➔ Strip-till is a minimum tillage practice. This practice combines the advantages of conventional tillage and the soil-protecting benefits of no-till, as the soil is only disturbed on the seed row.
- ➔ In our region, direct seeding is a common practice for grain crops, showing similar yield results to conventional tillage systems. In the specific case of sunflower, direct seeding is not a widespread practice, as no-tilled soil seems to be a problem for root development.
- ➔ Strip-till appears to be a practice that can solve this issues, as sunflower roots are able to explore soil depth while soil structure is preserved.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Ploughing and seedbed preparation.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Direct seeding has not shown good yield results on sunflower crop in the region.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Specific machinery, higher storage capacity...
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** No
- **Targeted crop categories:** oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, herbicides, storage
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fuel, Tractor working hours
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** More biodiversity, soil structure, lower labour intensity...
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** None

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **All features of the practice that may hinder its social acceptance:** logistics
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** YES, we avoid soil losses, reduce fuel use, improve water use...
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Eu member state: Spain

[Find out more](#)

Source of information Farmers

D2.3
Results of the GP & RI collection
process

Practice SQ n° 4

MANURE MEDIATION INCLUDING DIGESTED SEWAGE SLUDGE

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#manure mediation, organic carbon

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, Good Practice (GP), Sweden

Short description

- ➔ Manure mediation represents a strategy whereby farms with an abundance of organic manure can sell this resource to other farms that has a deficit of organic carbon in their system. This approach facilitates the transfer of nutrients from an area with a higher potential for nutrient leaching to an area with a demand for both nutrients and organic carbon and thereby enhancing soil quality.
- ➔ The idea is similar for mediation of digested sewage sludge, whereby this as well is transported to regions exhibiting a deficiency in such materials.
- ➔ This practice is conducted on a farm scale, with the farmer themselves determining the location of the greatest need for organic manure.
- ➔ The mediation and trade of the manure may be managed by advisory companies or by the farmers themselves. Through the advisory network, the farmers can receive assistance in testing the nutrient content of the manure and in determining its market value. The farmers contact the advisory company with information about how much and what kind of manure they have for sale. The prize of the manure is based on the nutrient content and distance of shipping distance.

- However, the supply of digested sludge is handled by specialised companies due to the regulations, analysis and contracts with the treatment plants. However, this is free of charge for farmers.
- The mediation of manure depends on the distance from the seller to the buyer, with the value of the manure decreasing with distance. Distance is not a problem for digested sewage sludge.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard practice for farms with an abundance of organic manure is to utilise it on their own farms. This leads to a risk of nitrogen and phosphorus leakage. Conversely, farms with no own production of organic manure may experience difficulties in providing organic carbon to the soil and has a hard time increase mulch.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? In Sweden, there are regions where dairy and beef production is the primary agricultural activity, and there are also regions where cereal production is the dominant agricultural practice. The presence of cattle in these areas results in a considerable supply of organic manure, which can lead to the leakage of nitrogen and phosphorus. However, these areas also exhibit a favourable supply of organic carbon and present an opportunity to enhance soil quality. Conversely, farms engaged in cereal production do not experience the same degree of nitrogen and phosphorus leakage. However, they face a more significant challenge in increasing mulch and enhancing soil quality.

Given the circumstances surrounding the increase in nitrogen prices, organic manure has become a more prominent source of nitrogen for cereal producers. This is due to a combination of factors, including the desire to increase mulch and improve soil quality.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: The strategy has been in place for some time. However, the subsequent rapid increase in nitrogen prices has had a positive effect on the valuation of organic manure.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes, loading (often with a wheel loader), transportation (truck), unloading (wheel loader), spreader.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** This can be used where organic manure can be used.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, fuel, transportation
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Reduced water use, more biodiversity

- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Less leaching for both nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium if the manure is spread correctly.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** digestate, animal manure, industrial waste, agricultural residues, municipal sludge, meat/bone meal.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Yes, there are regulations of when and how much of the manure a farmer may spread. It is often the phosphorus content that regulates the amount.
The policy barriers for digested sludge are more regulated. Digested sludge must be tested for heavy metals, salmonella and nutrient content. Again, the amount that can be spread depends on the phosphorus content.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes and no.
 - Manure Yes.
 - Digested sewage sludge No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** No
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** odor, logistics
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Perhaps the positive effects of organic manure are not widely known. People often react to the smell.
- People often have a negative opinion of digested sludge because they think it contains heavy metals and hormones.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, this is a win-win situation, both for the loss of nutrients and the increased soil quality.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information Manure mediation derived from farmer - to - farmer but some of the Hushållningssällskapen that could classifies as medium-sized companies expanded the activity and became a impartial third party

The company that developed the current procedure for the system of mediate digested sewage sludge is Ragn-Sells

The mediation of manure has from the beginning started at farm level where neighbours bought manure from each other. Today, some of Hushållningssällskapets companies do the mediating to give the farmers a helping hand with testing the nutrients, assessing the market value etc.

Practice SQ n° 5

OPTIMAL ORGANIC MATTER BALANCE

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Organic matter balance, quantification

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, Good Practice (GP), The Netherlands

Short description

- ➔ Calculating an organic matter balance provides insights into the inputs and outputs of organic matter within an agricultural system. Organic matter plays an important role in maintaining soil health, contributing to improved water retention, soil aeration, structure, and carbon sequestration. While many farmers recognize the importance of organic matter and understand the need to preserve or enhance its levels in the soil, the quantification of organic matter inputs and outputs is often overlooked. This is especially true over longer periods, where monitoring the organic matter balance over multiple years is rarely done.
- ➔ By accounting for both the inputs and outputs of organic matter, farmers can get a clear understanding of their farming system's long-term sustainability and the impacts on soil health. Inputs include sources such as crop residues, animal manure, cover crops, and compost. The output of organic matter is its degradation which is influenced by factors such as microbial degradation, crop growth, soil tillage practices, and external environmental conditions like rainfall and temperature.
- ➔ Estimating the degradation of organic matter might be challenging. However, there are standardized values that estimate the organic matter degradation rate per crop. Additionally, models that include additional factors like temperature, soil type and moisture can be used to make more precise estimations on the organic matter degradation rate.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Farmers rarely calculate their organic matter balance. Instead, the organic matter input is mostly based on the system (crop rotation/green manure use/crop residue management) that has been applied in the years before and on which external organic matter inputs are easily available/suits the way of working.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? A reduction in soil quality and organic matter content.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Multiple hours per year

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Multiple techniques
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** sandy, loamy, clay, silty, chalky
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Depending on the insights gained an adjustment in the organic matter input/output and therefore increased/lowered costs
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** N: no expected effect
- P: no expected effect
- K: no expected effect

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase

- May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture? No
- May the practice improve the farmer's self-image? No

Contact

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Wageningen Research

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Eu member state: The Netherlands

Find out more

Source of information

<https://www.handboekbodemenbemesting.nl/nl/handboekbodemenbemesting/ingangen/handeling/organische-stofbeheer/organische-stofbalans/kengetallen-organische-stof.htm>

Practice SQ n° 6

SPLIT N APPLICATION. FOR GRAIN CROPS, DIVIDING THE DOSE INTO 2 OR 3 SPLIT APPLICATIONS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Fertilizer efficiency, nitrogen

#SQ, food, fibre, oil, Good Practice (GP), Spain

Short description

➔ This practice is quite common in our region, and it is indeed one of the easiest ways to ensure fertilizer efficiency. Our recommendation is to split N application when the dose is higher than 120 NFU. When using this practice, farmers usually split N fertilizer in two separated applications, close to the moments when the crop has higher needs.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? The standard is to split N application in two separated applications. Some farmers even apply it in three times.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The main point is to reduce N losses to the environment.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Multiple techniques
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, fibre, oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** fuel
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** none
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Improve water quality
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:**
 - Nitrogen: Decrease
 - Phosphorus: none
 - Potassium: none

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** No
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: nitrous oxide, yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** applicable
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, reducing N leaching will lead to a reduction on water bodies contamination
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information INTIAs own fertilization trials

Practice SQ n° 7

SOIL LIMING

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Soil liming, acidic soils

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial, Good Practice (GP), Poland

Short description

➔ Due to sandy soils (70%) and climate, Poland has problems with soil acidification. Over 4 million hectares have a pH in KCl below 5.0 - such soils can be considered degraded - they have a damaged structure, plants are not able to absorb nutrients, which leads to water pollution. An additional problem is the fact that most of the acidic soils are owned by small farms. The practice consists in a wide action of soil pH analysis, establishment of liming programs and reimbursement of part of the costs from CAP funds - eco-schemes fertilization with liming.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Standard soil liming.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? This is the basic solution to improve the efficiency of management and protect the water environment.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: a longer period of time, due to the scale of the problem and the target audience - small farmers

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Costs, mechanization, transport over 50 mln ton of lime.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Just few techniques- soil analyse, lime spreading.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** sandy, loamy, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** fertilizers, equipment, fuel, transportation
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** skilled labour, herbicides, pesticides, fuel, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** increasing the efficiency of agricultural production, protecting water quality
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Main element to reduce leaching N and P from agricultural lands
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** meat/bone meal

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes- to the lime, soil analyse, advisory, popularization
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** lack of awareness among politicians and small farmers
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No, practice even allows to reduce the danger of absorbing heavy metals from the soil
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes - mainly
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** yes: ammonia
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** dust, change of the landscape, logistics
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** substantial increase

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information National State Report agricultural land in Poland: acidification of soils and their regeneration through liming - current state and proposals for systemic solutions

Additional info/links:

<http://phavi.wapno-info.pl/at/attachments/2022/0422/133556-spw-raport-zakwaszenie-gleb-wydanie-ii-luty-2022.pdf>

<https://www.bing.com/videos/riverview/relatedvideo?q=wapnowanie+gleby&mid=BC9481B300A74844D7FD&FORM=VAMTRV>

Practice SQ n° 8

CATCH CROPS

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#catch crops,

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial, Good Practice (GP), Poland

Short description

➔ A plant grown between two main crops for green fodder, hay, silage, ploughing as green manure or leaving in the form of mulch after they have been cut, dumped or destroyed by frost.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Cultivation of white mustard.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? preparation of the ground for sowing seeds, mulching, ploughing.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: 1 year

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Sowing time, weather conditions.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Multiple techniques
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** fuel, transportation, unskilled labour, equipment
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** skilled labour, fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** 1 year
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** For all of them decreasing

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** substantial increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** environmental protection, scenic and aesthetic values, green agriculture
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** awareness of modern management

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information <https://www.gov.pl/web/rolnictwo>

Practice SQ n° 9

IOCONCIV INTRODUCTION AND OPTIMIZATION OF TECHNIQUES AND SYSTEMS FOR CONTROL OF VINEYARD WEED FLORA

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Reduce herbicides, cover crops

#SQ, food, oil, industrial, Good Practice (GP), Italy

Short description

- ➔ The general objective is to reduce the use of herbicides in Tuscan vineyards (glyphosate in particular) and improve the fertility of vineyard soils. The proposed innovation involves the use of cover crops under the vine rows in order to reduce the use of herbicides or soil tillage with consequent economic and environmental benefits.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? In the Region, practices are different, it depends on area and knowledge of the farmers.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Weed control in the sub-row, the decrease in soil fertility, the loss of biodiversity, soil erosion and the increase in the use of chemicals represent the weak points of most of the Tuscan winemaking system.

The project tested eco-friendly techniques in 4 farms with different soil characteristics and management systems (conventional and organic). Each farm tested 3 soil and weed management systems in the vineyard during a period of 3 years. The management systems tested were: (TA) conventional system based on soil tillage under and between the rows + application of herbicide under the row (for conventional agriculture); (PI) grassing of the sub-row with *Trifolium subterraneum* + inter-row managed conventionally; (TI) grassing of the sub-row with *Trifolium subterraneum* + grassing of the inter-row with a mixture of different species. Grassing significantly improved the carbon balance by increasing carbon sequestration in soil and biomass and reducing emissions.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: It Took 44 months

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** The project needed and developed a prototype to work under-row and/or inter-row cultivation.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** yes for trees
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, oil, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, fuel, land, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Yes
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** There is any leaching
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** biochar

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** yes, from CAP
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** We do not use eco-scheme for these intervention
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No

- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes,
 - The innovative techniques tested proved to be economically and environmentally sustainable.
 - The grassing significantly improved the carbon balance by increasing its sequestration in the soil and biomass and reducing emissions.
 - and it is the case since it contributes to soil quality improvement, water use improvement.

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information Data base of RDP projects in particular Operational Group

Additional info/links: IOCONCIV <https://www.ioconciv.it/>

Practice SQ n° 10

ORTOBIOATTIVO: AGROECOLOGY FOR THE SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION OF NUTRACEUTICAL VEGETABLES

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#Vegetable cultivation, resilient plants

#SQ, food, ornamental, industrial, Research Innovation (RI), Italy

Short description

- Development and adoption of a new agronomic approach for vegetable cultivation called “Ortobioattivo. This model focuses on the quality of the substrate/soil and the microbiological biodiversity contained therein as a fundamental element for the cultivation of healthy plants, capable of defending themselves almost autonomously from pathogens and capable of being naturally rich in nutrients of interest for human health (nutraceutical bioactive substances).

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Generally, use of fertilizers or bio fertilizers.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? The creation and management of a bioactive garden are easy to implement, and this makes the system replicable and transferable not only in horticultural companies present in the area affected by the cooperation project but also in those present in other regional and extra-regional territorial realities.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: It took 32 Months

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Not in particular
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Horticulture cultivation
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, ornamental, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, clay, sandy, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, land, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Yes
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** there are not leaching
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** micro-organisms, agricultural residues, plant extracts

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** none
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Find out more

Source of information Data bank for RDP projects

Additional info/links: <https://www.ortobioattivopsgo.unifi.it/>

Practice SQ n° 11

REDUCING SOIL TILLAGE / SIMPLIFIED CULTIVATION TECHNIQUES

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Reduced tillage, biological activity

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial, Good Practice (GP), France

Short description

→ Simplified cultivation techniques are practices to reduce soil tillage, without use of ploughing. Their use allows to prevent from erosion and to improve soil biological activity, particularly earthworm presence. Simplified cultivation techniques gather deep ploughing (or ploughing without turnaround), crop itinerary with non-plough tillage but loosening, strip till, superficial tillage and direct sowing.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Conventional ploughing.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? This kind of practice can be need because of issues of soil fertility like packing or plough pan. In a situation of wet and hot climate, ploughing may occur erosion. An intensive soil work decreases the content of organic matter of the arable lay by accelerating its mineralisation. A decrease of soil tillage may also improve the sustainability of the soil helper macrofauna.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: About 3-5 years are needed to get effects.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Changing the tillage practices may need new farm equipment.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** There are numerous practices that make up the framework of simplified cultivation techniques: for example, the decrease of ploughing use and the substitution of plow by another equipment like cultivator.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** silty, chalky, loamy, clay, sandy, peaty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** herbicides, equipment
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** unskilled labour, fuel, equipment, energy
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Simplified cultivation techniques reduce labor and fuel costs through less frequent field visits. Thus, it is estimated that TCS can reduce fuel consumption by 20 to 40% compared to the conventional system. A french study in 2006 and 2007 in 11 regions proposes an evolution for the sowing costs from 167 €/ha in the situation of conventional ploughing to 84 -156 €/ha with simplified cultural techniques (<https://www.arvalis.fr/infos-techniques/les-economies-de-charges-la-cle>).
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** decrease/decrease/none

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** It depends on local policy
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Partially
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Theoretically but not in practice
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

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Eu member state: France

Find out more

Source of information French COP workshop on September the 4th 2024 at Angers

Practice SQ n° 12

COVER CROP MIXING GRASSES AND LEGUMES

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#cover crop, grasses

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial, Good Practice (GP), France

Short description

➔ Between two main crops is sown a mixture of grasses - oats, rye, buckwheat, Moha - and legumes - often forage species, instead of a bare soil. The cover crop is destroyed during its vegetative step before the seed formation.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Bare soils are still present during the winter period.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? To prevent soils from erosion and leaching thanks to the leaf and the root areas with the caption of a part of the mineral nitrogen still stored in the soil after the harvest. To fix soil structural issues like packing or slaking crust thanks to the root action and to the earthworms' activity improved by the organic matter provided by the cover crop. To maintain or increase the soil organic matter content and to balance the mineralisation impacts. To break the chain of parasites or diseases.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: This practice needs two more interventions after harvest during the autumn and winter period. No specific measure to be taken.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** This practice requires to buy or to product seeds for the cover crop and two operations of seeding and destroying.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** This practice is designed for the crop rotations with a long intercrop period - Rapeseed / Corn for example.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** unskilled labour, fuel, storage, energy
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Better organic matter content - better soil structure - better resilience against hydric stress - better availability of nutrients - better water quality.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** decrease/decrease/decrease

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** It is a possibility with local programs applied to water catchment areas
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** well-developed
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Rules about cover crops from transcription of Nitrate directive are not good agronomical rules enough
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** negative: GHG emissions may increase due to the implementation of the practice
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, with a positive effect on the landscape by keeping a vegetal presence during a longer period
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes

Contact

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Eu member state: France

Find out more

Source of information French COP workshop on September the 4th 2024 at Angers + written sources

Additional info/links:

Article (in French) : IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATE CROPS ON THE CHEMICAL AND BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF SOILS (IMPACT DES CULTURES INTERMEDIAIRES SUR LES PROPRIETES CHIMIQUES ET BIOLOGIQUES DES SOLS) - https://agriressources.fr/fileadmin/user_upload/Auvergne-Rhone-Alpes/177_Eve-agriressources/fertisols/RESSOURCES/Ameliorations/Nov2015-Comifer-Gemas-ARTICLE-LABREUCHE-

[impacts-couverts-sols.pdf](#)

D2.3
Results of the GP & RI collection
process

Brochure (in French) : FOR OPTIMIZED MANAGEMENT OF SOIL FERTILITY (POUR UNE GESTION OPTIMISÉE DE LA FERTILITÉ DES SOLS) - <https://agriressources.fr/fertisols/>

Practice SQ n° 13

CROP ROTATION

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Crop rotation, nutrients

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, Good Practice (GP), The Netherlands

Short description

- Crop rotation is an important factor in maintaining and improving soil health. Continuously growing the same crop over multiple years can lead to an increase in soilborne diseases, as pathogens specific to that crop are given the opportunity to multiply. When a susceptible crop is repeatedly grown in a short amount of time, these diseases can spread more easily, reducing plant health and yield. Similarly, an intensive crop rotation of a limited number of crops can deplete the nutrient availability.
- In contrast, a diverse crop rotation that includes a variety of plant species, particularly deep-rooted and cover crops, contributes to better soil structure and overall soil health. By alternating crops with different root systems and nutrient needs, farmers can reduce soil compaction, improve aeration, and enhance organic matter content. Including legumes in the rotation, such as clover, can increase nitrogen levels through nitrogen fixation. This is especially relevant in organic farming.
- Furthermore, integrating crops with varying nutrient demands and decomposition rates helps balance nutrient cycling. Deep-rooting crops, for example, can access nutrients from deeper soil layers, which, after their residues decompose, become available to shallow-rooting crops. In addition, alternating between crops with different functions, such as leaf and root crops, not only diversifies nutrient usage but also reduces pest and disease pressures by breaking their life cycles, can contribute to weed control and spread the labour demands.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Depending on the region a rotation of 1:2 to 1:4.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Expanding the crop rotation is a systemic change in the farm management. It does not only change the

machinery required, but also affects the profitability of the farm. Reducing the number of intensive crops might lower the financial profits but could potentially also lower the costs. Especially when the investment results in a higher yield per hectare in the year that the cash crop is grown.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** No
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Annual crops
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** skilled labour, storage
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** They could both increase and decrease, depending on the positive effects on soil health and the reduction in costs.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** This depends on the change in crop rotation, and the consideration of mineralisation. Overall, it is expected to decrease for all the nutrients.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** change of the landscape
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, it would break the perspective of a monoculture.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** No

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Find out more

Source of information <https://edepot.wur.nl/11786>

Practice SQ n° 14

BIOASHES FOR ADVANCED AGRI-FOOD PRODUCTION & SOIL FERTILITY

Introduction

Category: Good practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Bioash, pedological survey

#SQ, Food, feed, fibre ,oil, industrial, Good practice (GP), Croatia

Short description

- The utilization of bioashes in Croatia presents a valuable opportunity for sustainable disposal and agroforestry applications. These alkaline by-products, derived from forest biomass plants, can effectively address the challenge of acidic soil (pH < 6) by enhancing soil fertility and reducing the need for mineral fertilizers and commercial conditioners.
- At the beginning of the project, we analysed the needs and key goals were identified - to prove the usability of using ash from the biomass thermal power plant for the purpose of improving agricultural production

and the fertility of agricultural areas on acidic and poorly supplied soils with P, K and other macro-/micro-elements. Soil samples were taken from partner-managed plots for initial screening and analysis of pH, P, K, and humus content. Detailed pedological research was conducted on selected plots, including morphological analysis and physio-chemical laboratory analyses. A 2-year field experiment with bioash treatments was carried out, monitoring soil changes, microbiology, and crop yield. Over 400 soil samples were analyzed for physical-chemical and microbiological properties. Plant material was also tested for yield and nutrient content.

- Through years of extensive research in both field and controlled settings, the project has investigated the impact of different bioash doses on physico-chemical and microbiological properties of acid soils, as well as the qualitative and quantitative parameters of agricultural crops. The project resulted in increased soil fertility and innovative products for soil amelioration, recognized with awards for sustainability and waste management.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Conventional agricultural practice, which include using of mineral fertilizers and pesticides.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Acidic and poorly supplied soils with P, K and other macro-/micro-elements.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: A 2-year field experiment with bioash treatments was carried out, monitoring soil changes, microbiology, and crop yield.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** The original form of biomass ash is a fine, powdery substance with a highly alkaline nature. As such, its application in the field requires specialized equipment designed for handling dusty materials. To ensure safe and effective use, application should be conducted on windless days to minimize the risk of dispersion and potential environmental impact.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Yes, the project is based on the implementation of several years of research activities in the field and under controlled conditions, where the influence of the application of different doses of bioash on physico-chemical and microbiological changes in acid soils as well as qualitative-quantitative parameters of agricultural crops will be studied. The project will also lead to the development of new bioash-based products with the potential for wider application in the chemical remediation of acidic soils. It can be applied to a multitude of cultivation practice.
- **Targeted crop categories:** Food, feed, fibre, oil, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** clay, loamy
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** transportation
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, pesticides
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Reduction in the use of conventionally expensive soil conditioners and mineral fertilizers: the use of biomass ash can reduce the need for the use of expensive soil conditioners and mineral fertilizers, resulting in a reduction of production costs and the negative environmental impact associated with the production and application of mineral fertilizers and the promotion of sustainable practices in the agricultural sector. The development of effective and sustainable soil amelioration strategies, including the recycling of potentially valuable waste materials (accumulation in world ~ 700 Mt/year, EU ~15.5 Mt/year in Croatia ~100 000 t/year), could offer a more sustainable approach compared to certain commercial products used for soil fertility and crop performance in acid soils.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** The application of biomass ash effectively ameliorated the acid and nutrient-deficient soil, leading to a substantial increase in soil pH and

concentration of key nutrients (P, K, Ca), without soil contamination.

- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** Industrial waste, agriculture residues

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Yes. There is no regulation in terms of application (which dose of bioash, how many times during some time, etc.)
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** It is important to emphasize the inherent diversity of biomass ash matrices, which are influenced by numerous factors. Specifically, the physicochemical composition of bioash matrices depends on: i) the type of ash,
- ii) the biomass source, iii) combustion parameters, iv) post-combustion. It's important to analyze physicochemical properties of biomass ash to confirm that the levels of organic pollutants (e.g., PAHs, PCBs) and potentially toxic trace elements (e.g., Cd, Mo, Pb, Hg, As, Cr, Co) in the tested bioash are below the maximum permitted concentrations for agricultural soil application.
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes, it is. Our study addresses significant knowledge gaps by exploring the unique potential of the bioash matrix in ameliorating acidic soils under field and organic farming conditions.
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** dust
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** none
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes. Increasing soil fertility with less use of mineral P and K fertilizers and other commercial soil conditioners (various calcareous materials, fractions of limestone and dolomite) to neutralize acidic soils. Increasing the productivity and profitability of agricultural holdings. Encouraging innovation and application of new technologies in agriculture. Increasing awareness of the importance of sustainable agriculture and environmental protection. Creating preconditions for smart and competitive agriculture. Improving processes for environmental protection, adaptation and mitigation of climate change (application of biomass ash fits into the sustainable and efficient management of by-products from biomass power plants).
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes. Project provides opportunities for farmers to enhance their skills, knowledge and experience in modern agricultural practices, with special attention to the sustainability. Their active involvement in the development and promotion of sustainable practices in agriculture has supported their career development in the field. Also, participation in the project enabled them to establish connections and partnerships with other experts and organizations and expanded the network of contacts.
- **Other relevant information:** The methods and technologies developed in the project can be applied in other areas of Croatia and abroad. The experiences and results of the project, as well as the developed innovative products, can be useful to farmers, researchers and interested stakeholders who face similar problems and challenges of managing biomass ash as a by-product for the purpose of improving soil fertility, with adaptations to the specific conditions and needs of a certain area. Also, the project can serve as a model and source of inspiration for the implementation of similar innovative solutions in other areas. Active participation and successful cooperation between universities, research institutions, farmers and rural stakeholders in research activities and application of results, that provided an opportunity for direct application of new knowledge and techniques in real environment, encouraging sustainability and local development.

Contact

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Eu member state: Croatia

Find out more

Source of information EIP-AGRI Project database

Additional info/links:

Bioashes for advanced agri-food production & soil fertility,

https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/bioashes-advanced-agri-food-production-soil-fertility-ash4soil_en#tab_id=overview

Practice SQ n° 15

POSSIBILITIES OF USING BIOGAS DIGESTATE PLANTS AS FERTILIZERS AND SOIL IMPROVERS

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#Fertilizer trial, digestate

#SQ, food, feed, Research Innovation (RI), Croatia

Slika 5.
Uzimanje uzoraka tla
za fizikalne analize

Slika 6.
Vlaženje uzoraka tla

Slika 7.
Osušeni uzorci
za fizikalne analize

Slika 8.
Određivanje gustoće
čvrstih čestica

Short description

→ Fertilizer trials will be set up on agricultural land OPGs on three crops in crop rotation/rotation: maize, winter wheat, and Italian ryegrass. Before setting up the experiment, soil samples will be taken in the planned areas in order to determine the initial state, and the analysis of the digestate that will be used in the research will be carried out. The second step will be setting up experiments and implementing all necessary agrotechnical measures. In accordance with the research plan, soil and plant samples will be continuously taken and analyzed material and perform all necessary measurements in the experiment. Yields per variant will be determined by fertilization and production costs and profitability for each variant of the experiment.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** A lot of methanization.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Yes, variants of fertilization were: the application of exclusively mineral fertilizers (basic fertilization, starter fertilization, and top dressing) or application of solid or liquid digestate in basic fertilization

with the addition of mineral fertilizers.

- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** clay, peaty, chalky
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** increase
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** equipment, fertilizers, fuel, transportation, energy
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, unskilled labour
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** On the basis of economic profitability from the aspect of fertilization and realized yields, fertilization with liquid digestate is more profitable, but in the long term, fertilization is recommended to improve soil fertility solid digestate.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** In liquid digestate there was more nutrients.
- **Specific materials applicated through the practice:** Digestate

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** existing, however with gaps
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No.
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** no
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** logistics
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** Time-saving
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes
- **Other relevant information:** Active participation and successful cooperation between universities, research institutions, farmers and rural stakeholders in research activities and application of results, that provided an opportunity for direct application of new knowledge and techniques in real environment, encouraging sustainability and local development.

Contact

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Eu member state: Croatia

Find out more

Additional info/links:

Brochure of the project

Practice SQ n° 16

PREVENTING AND RESOLVING SOIL COMPACTION

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Soil compaction, tillage

#SQ, food, feed, industrial, fibre, oil, ornamental, Good Practice (GP), Belgium

Short description

- ➔ The prevention of soil compaction by reducing the load per cm^2 of soil and by taking care of the soil's carrying capacity is very important because the resolving of deep soil compaction (compaction just below the topsoil, 30-50 cm) is difficult. Resolving of deep soil compaction can be done by a combination of deep tilling, deep rooting crops and subsequent maximal prevention of re-compaction.
- ➔ Reducing the load per cm^2 of soil can be done by optimization of tyre size and pressure, by dividing the load over several wheels, by minimizing the total load as much as possible and by using semi-mounted machinery. In addition, the carrying capacity of the soil against compaction needs to be considered and this is much lower when the soil is wet and when it is freshly cultivated.
- ➔ Deep tilling to resolve soil compaction needs to be considered carefully. After deep tilling, deep rooted crops should be cultivated and measures that ensure maximal prevention for re-compaction need to be taken. Deep tilling, when done careless, can result in even deeper and stronger compaction. The use of deep rooting crops only is likely not sufficient to resolve deep compaction.
- ➔ Conservation tillage practices have less deep compaction.

→ In some cases, use of fixed field pathways via RTK-GPS navigation can prevent compaction in the remaining field, often done in intensive vegetable production.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? none

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice?

Reduced crop yield in compacted areas.

How long did it take to implement the practice, and which are the measures needed to monitor: Farmers need to be aware of the risks of soil compaction when going into their fields when the soil is too wet and with too heavy loads. There is need for a mentality shift but there is also the need for adaptations on the tractors and the rest of their machinery. We estimate it will take 3-5 seasons to implement the practise with a new farmer.

Farmers often know their “bad spots” in the field. In those spots, during wintertime, using a penetrometer (either digital or manual) can help investigate whether these bad spots are due to deep soil compaction. Deep soil compaction = compaction just below the top soil (30-50 cm). Use of a penetrometer should be done when soil is at field capacity, penetration of soil should be very easy then. Resistance against penetration can indicate soil compaction.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Prevention of soil compaction is a very logistic measure, e.g., tyre pressure needs to be adapted when entering the field, total loads need to be minimized as much as possible and when the soil’s carrying capacity is too low (e.g. wet soil) it can be better to move soil cultivation or other farm activities until drier periods. This is not always possible (e.g. harvest of late crops, fertilizing nearby or past critical sowing periods), then minimizing of the load per cm² is critical. This can even be achieved by use of a smaller harvest trailers on the field in combination with bigger ones next to the field or by only half-filling manure tanks.
- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Must be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques, from fertilizer application to soil cultivation, sowing and harvesting.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, industrial, fibre, oil, ornamental
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** sandy, clay, loamy, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** unskilled labour, skilled labour, equipment, transportation
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fuel
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Prevention (and resolving) of soil compaction will lead to higher yields.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Not clear. In theory, better root development of

crops in non-compacted soil should increase nutrient uptake, thus lower leaching losses. But at the moment there is not sufficient proof of that.

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Some parts of this practise qualify for subsidies. For example, the Flemish government provides partial financing of pressure exchange systems and low-pressure tyres.
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** Yes, policy related to influencing timing of land practices decreases the flexibility of the farmers to plan the work according to the day by day climatic conditions, which is necessary when taking the soil's carrying capacity maximally into account.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes, some specific applications. For example, sowing a multi-annual alfalfa could help protect the soil against re-compaction after deep drilling and is part of the CAP ecoschemes. In addition, practising no-till could prevent deep compaction to worsen or even improve over time.
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** It should. When farmers take care of the soil, this has positive effects beyond their production, e.g., towards water management.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, taking care for the soil is taking care for the future.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: Soil Service of Belgium/ILVO
Contact information of the FIN partner: mverbeeck@bdb.be
Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information Practical research, published in written sources.

Additional info/links:

Elsen F., Beckers V., Diels J., Van Orshoven J., Wauters S., Huybrechts M. (2014). Praktijkonderzoek naar de toepassing van preventieve en remediërende maatregelen tegen bodemaantasting door bodemverdichting. Studie uitgevoerd in opdracht van de Vlaamse Overheid, Dep. Leefmilieu, Natuur en Energie, Afd. Land en Bodembescherming, Ondergrond, Natuurlijke Rijkdommen, door

de Bodemkundige Dienst van België, het Departement Aard- en Omgevingswetenschappen (KU Leuven) en Thomas More (KU Leuven Associatie). 314 pp.
(<https://archieff.algemeen.omgeving.vlaanderen.be/xmlui/handle/acd/450128>)

Vanderhasselt, A., Cool, S., D'Hose, T., & Cornelis, W. (2023). How tine characteristics of subsoilers affect fuel consumption, penetration resistance and potato yield of a sandy loam soil. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2022.105631>

Vanderhasselt, A., D'Hose, T., Sneyders, M., & Cornelis, W. (2024). Effects of road- vs. field-recommended tyre inflation pressures and small variations in soil moisture content on traffic-induced soil compaction during seedbed preparation. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2024.106109>

Vanderhasselt, A., Euben, R., D'hose, T., & Cornelis, W. (2022). Slurry Spreading on a Silt Loam Soil: Influence of Tyre Inflation Pressure, Number of Passages, Machinery Choice and Tillage Method on Physical Soil Quality and Sugar Beet Growth. *Land*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11060913>

Vanderhasselt, A., Steinwiddler, L., D'Hose, T., & Cornelis, W. (2024). Opening up the subsoil: Subsoiling and bio-subsoilers to remediate subsoil compaction in three fodder crop rotations on a sandy loam soil. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2023.105956>

Practice SQ n° 17

QUALITY FODDER – QUALITY MANURE – QUALITY SOIL

Introduction

Category: Research Innovation (RI)

Practice identity card

#Manure quality, diversification

#SQ, feed, food, Research Innovation (RI), Belgium

Short description

- ➔ Changing the crop rotation towards more grass (single, multispecies, with legumes) in a fodder producing agricultural system for cattle production will positively benefit soil quality by breaking monoculture (or dominance) silage maize, a crop with very low contribution to soil organic matter and changing to crops that have large contribution to soil organic matter (grasses). In addition, diversifying the crop rotation increases diversity and the possibility of having perennial crops is higher, which has an additional positive impact to soil quality, by less disturbance of the soil.
- ➔ In addition, it is hypothesized that the manure produced by cattle fed by this shifted ration (from dominance silage maize to more grass-based) has a higher “quality” which would have positive effects on soil quality. Examples are an increased C/N ratio of the manure, more N in organic forms and a

shifted microbial composition. This could lead to higher contribution of the manure to soil organic matter and changes in the soil microbial composition.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Fodder production with dominance of silage maize.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Regulations regarding NH₃-emissions in cattle farming. Some farmers indicate poor cattle health as a driver in changing the feed rations towards more grass.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Monitoring: characterisation of fodder composition in combination with manure and soil characterisation.

Logistics

- **Skill/education level required:** rather high

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** Limited to (dairy) cattle production.
- **Targeted crop categories:** feed, food
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** peaty, sandy, clay, loamy, chalky, silty
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** increase
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** decrease
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** none
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Less costs in veterinary costs, less fertilizer costs, better N-use efficiency of applied manure.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** In theory less leaching of N when manure has more N in organic forms, it could act as a slow-release fertilizer, with higher N use efficiency.
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** animal manure

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** Yes, many subsidies under the CAP
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** No
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** No
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** Yes, changing arable field to grass, change temporary grass to permanent grass, growing annual protein-rich crops, growing perennial protein-rich crops, increased crop rotation with legumes, increase soil organic carbon by crop rotation
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** little or none

- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, improving soil quality by increasing soil organic matter for example has secondary benefits for society, e.g., water management in better structured soils due to higher SOM.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, taking care for the soil is taking care for the future.

Contact

Name of the FIN (Fertilization Innovation Network) partner submitting the information: Soil Service of Belgium

Contact information of the FIN partner: mverbeeck@bdb.be

Eu member state: Belgium

Find out more

Source of information Scientific expertise, farm advisor expertise in written and spoken form, from farm advisors and from pioneer farmers.

Additional info/links:

Vanhoof, P. & Nigten, A. (2020). Drijfmest, invloeden op emissies, N-benutting op grasland. Eindrapport van onderzoek naar stikstof in de kringloop. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fM2OrgiHu4E>
<https://www.actimin.nl/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/2020-12-EINDRAPPORT-DRIJFMEST-EMISSIES-EN-STIKSTOFBENUTTING.pdf>

Practice SQ n° 18

BIOCHAR AS SOIL AMENDMENT

Introduction

Category: Good Practice (GP)

Practice identity card

#Biochar, soil resilience

#SQ, food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial, Good Practice (GP), Sweden

Short description

- ➔ Biochar is used as a soil amendment due to its properties of storing water and nutrients. It is also a carbon sink and can thereby be sold as a carbon credit, giving the farmer an additional revenue stream.
- ➔ Biochar is applied on or in the soil, can be applied together or separately from manure, seeds or while otherwise working the land. There is no generally accepted limit to how much biochar can be applied, but in field studies around 8 tons dry matter per hectare is commonly used.

Implementation process

Which practice is considered as the standard in this region? Soil amendments have been used on most soils and have included the addition of manure, straw or other organic matters. Nutrients have also basically always been added to agricultural lands but in the form of mineral fertilizers. Biochar takes the role of both these amendments, with the addition of being a carbon sink.

What was the on-farm issue/challenge/opportunity that led to the implementation of the practice? Climate change issues provided the opportunity to gain financially from producing biochar and selling the carbon credits. On-farm challenges of soil packing, lack of nutrients, lack of soil carbon, and the increased threat of drought backed the solution of using biochar as a soil amendment.

How long did it take to implement the practice and which are the measures needed to monitor: Same time as spreading fertilizer or manure. No monitoring needed for the carbon sink.

Logistics

- **Logistic aspects to consider:** Yes. Biochar is flammable and should be stored accordingly. It is also very dusty when handled so proper safety equipment should be used (e.g. air filters).

- **Skill/education level required:** rather low

Agronomical traits

- **Can the practice be applied to a multitude of cultivation techniques?** It can be used for most cultivation techniques. It is especially suitable for cascading techniques where for example first can be used in the feed for cattle, the manure ends up in a biogas plant, from there it goes to a manure well and on to its final destination the soil.
- **Targeted crop categories:** food, feed, fibre, oil, ornamental, industrial
- **Soil types suitable for the practice:** All, but the effect of will vary depending on the characteristics of both the biochar and the soil
- **Expected effect on crop yield:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop yield variation:** decrease
- **Expected effect on crop quality:** similar
- **Expected effect on crop quality variation:** similar
- **Which costs may increase due to the practice?** You either have to buy the biochar or produce it (investment cost)
- **Which costs may decrease due to the practice?** fertilizers
- **Expected long-term/indirect economic benefits of the practice:** Increased income from carbon credits. Increased resilience in the soil e.g. against droughts and floods.
- **Expected effect on the leaching of nutrients:** Decreased leaching
- **Specific materials applied through the practice:** biochar

Administrative context

- **Does the practice qualify for subsidies?** No (might differ between countries)
- **Status of the legal framework that regulates the practice:** there is hardly any
- **Are there any policy barriers complicating the practice's application?** The EU CRCF regulatory framework will have a large impact on the voluntary carbon credit market. As a soil amendment there are hardly any regulations or policies.
- **Does the practice involve the use of hazardous substances?** Biochar is flammable and dusty but generally not considered hazardous.
- **Is the practice compliant with EU organic farming practices?** Yes
- **Is the practice supported by Eco-schemes?** It should be since it can be considered a carbon farming technique. But I would need to read up further to see if it is mentioned in the eco-schemes.
- **Are there any gaseous emissions to be considered upon application of the practice?** No
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) reduction potential of the practice:** substantial
- **All features of the practice than may hinder its social acceptance:** dust
- **Expected effects from the practice on the time occupation of the farmer?** moderate increase
- **May the practice contribute to a better public image of agriculture?** Yes, as it will increase the stable carbon sinks and decrease the CO₂ in the atmosphere.
- **May the practice improve the farmer's self-image?** Yes, it gives a feeling of doing something good for a sustainable use of the soil as well as being a climate hero.

Contact

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Eu member state: Sweden

Find out more

Source of information Project: E.g. Carbon credits by biochar, <https://hushallningsallskapet.se/vara-projekt-och-uppdrag/kolsankratter-med-biokol/> EIP, start 2020, end 2025

Practical experience from e.g. Hjlemsäters Egendom (<https://www.biokol.se/>)

Additional info/links:

There are thousands of scientific articles on biochar as a soil amendment.